

CITIZEN-SDSS PROJECT: STUDY LANDSCAPES PROFILE PHILIPPINES

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1 Introduction

The CITIZEN-SDSS project is focused on fostering nature-based solutions (NBS) for sustaining and expanding the remaining forest landscapes in the Philippines by integrating local stakeholder aspirations into land use planning through spatial decision support systems (SDSS). The Philippines, with only 24% of its forest cover remaining, faces severe threats from deforestation, degradation, and climate change, despite being a global biodiversity hotspot and a vital provider of ecosystem services and livelihoods. By focusing on the Philippines, the project addresses both urgent ecological risks and pressing socio-economic needs thus, safeguarding biodiversity, supporting local communities through NBS interventions such as agroforestry, forest restoration, assisted natural regeneration (ANR), riparian buffer restoration and other sustainable land management practices. Through Citizen Science approaches and spatiotemporal modelling, CITIZEN-SDSS develops context-sensitive, scientifically rigorous pathways for sustainable land and forest management, ensuring that decision-making processes are inclusive, locally grounded, and responsive to long-term environmental and livelihood priorities.

2 Study regions

The project mainly focuses on two regions in the Philippines which includes Cagayan Valley, termed as Region 2 and Eastern Visayas, termed as Region 8. These two regions exhibit some of the remaining intact forest landscapes of the Philippines (Gabriel et al., 2025) and ongoing reforestation and landscape restoration projects (under the umbrella of NBS) (Ferrer Velasco et al., 2022), however, there exist different patterns of land use changes characterised with continuous occurrence of deforestation and forest degradation. The Deforestation and forest degradation in these regions is mainly caused by cropland area expansion, illegal logging, charcoal making, fuelwood extraction, among others (Rose et al., 2009).

2.1 Cagayan Valley – Region II

The Cagayan Valley Region is located in the north-eastern part of Luzon, is the largest valley in the Philippines and is often referred to as the country's "rice and corn granary." The region is bounded by the Sierra Madre and Cordillera Mountain ranges, it is traversed by the Cagayan River, the longest river in the Philippines. The region is rich in fertile agricultural lands, vast forests, and abundant natural resources, making it a key area for farming, forestry, and fisheries. It is also highly biodiverse, with parts of the Sierra Madre recognized as critical habitats. Cagayan valley is characterised mainly as a type II and some areas type III climatic zone with no pronounced season (Coronas, 1920; Corporal-Lodangco, Leslie 2017), but a relatively wet period from May to October and vulnerable to natural disasters like floods and typhoons (PSA, 2023).

2.2 Eastern Visayas – Region VIII

The Eastern Visayas Region is located in the central Philippines, bounded by the Pacific Ocean, Samar Sea, and Leyte Gulf. The region is known for its uneven terrain, rich coastal resources, and extensive forests, the region is both agriculturally productive and highly biodiverse. It is a major producer of coconut, abaca, and fisheries, while also being home to important protected areas. The region find itself in the type III climatic zone of the Philippines (Coronas, 1920; Corporal-Lodangco, Leslie 2017) and experience rainfall throughout the year with no distinct dry season, and considered to be highly vulnerable to natural hazards such as typhoons, floods, and storm surges, exemplified by Typhoon Haiyan (Yolanda) in 2013, making resilience and sustainable land management critical for its future (DOST, 2017).

3 Study landscapes

The CITIZEN-SDSS project specifically focuses on four different landscapes from the above mentioned two regions, namely, **Penablanca** and **Balasig Watershed** from Region 2 and **Maasin** and **Silago** from Region 8. The subsequent sections of this report provide descriptions of these landscapes in terms of their socio-demographic characteristics, land use and topography, climatic conditions and future projections, future land use and forest management visions as well as current and potential future management challenges, mainly extracted from the

respective landscapes Comprehensive Land Use Plans (CLUPs) (Cadiz et al., 2022; City of Maasin, 2016; Municipality of Cabagan, 2018; Municipality of Penablanca, 2020; Municipality of Tumauni, 2023).

3.1 Penablanca

3.1.1 Socio-demographic

Penablanca municipality is located in Cagayan Province of the Cagayan Valley Region, consisting of 24 barangays and generally considered an intermediate rural-urban area. The municipality has a total land area of 1,245.65 km² (124,565 hectares), of which nearly 67% is forestland, much of it falling within the Peñablanca Protected Landscape and Seascape (PPLS). The 2024 population of the landscape stood at 50856 with a gross population density of 40 persons per km² (0.41 person per ha), and a declining growth rate since 2010 (see Fig 1 and Table 1). Agriculture, thus, primarily corn and rice farming remain the dominant source of livelihood, while the emerging sectors of quarrying, commerce, and eco-tourism supplement income opportunities mostly in the urban centers of the municipality (Municipality of Penablanca, 2020).

Table 1: Total population of Penablanca from 2010 to 2024

Year	Total Population
2010	42,736
2015	48,584
2020	50,300
2024	50,856

Source: <https://psa.gov.ph/>

Figure 1: Population growth rate trend (annual % change) of Penablanca from 2010 to 2024

Source: <https://psa.gov.ph/>

3.1.2 Land use and topography

Penablanca’s topography is highly varied, consisting of alluvial plains and valleys along the western portion and extensive hilly to mountainous terrain in the east dominated by the Sierra Madre Mountain range, which covers about 85% of the municipality. Elevations range from 51 meters in the lowlands to over 1,814 meters above sea level in the uplands, with slopes exceeding 50% across more than 40% of the total land area (Fig. 2). These steep

and rugged landscapes play a critical role in shaping land use, limiting large-scale settlements and agriculture in higher elevations while supporting forests, watersheds, and biodiversity habitats that are central to the municipality’s ecological and socio-economic systems.

Figure 2: Topography of Penablanca

Source: Research team construct using municipality and barangay administrative boundaries from Penablanca Local Government Unit (LGU) and elevation map using DEM from Aster (<https://asterweb.jpl.nasa.gov/gdem.asp>)

Table 2: Penablanca land cover coverage (ha and km²) and percentage of coverage to total land area

Land cover class	Area (ha)	Area (km ²)	% Coverage
Closed forest	33023.97	330.24	26.53
Open forest	50895.09	508.95	40.89
Mangrove	27.99	0.28	0.02
Shrubs	12173.94	121.74	9.78
Bareland	640.62	6.41	0.52
Grassland	8667.18	86.67	6.96
Annual cropland	16723.26	167.23	13.44
Perennial cropland	494.19	4.94	0.4
Built_up	658.98	6.59	0.53
Water	1160.37	11.6	0.93

Source: Researchers’ construct using land cover data from NAMRIA <https://geoportal.gov.ph/>

Penablanca land use dominated is by forest cover that accounts for more than two-thirds of the landscape according to National Mapping and Resource Information Authority (NAMRIA) land cover 2020 (see Table 2 and Fig. 3). Open forest is the largest class, covering about 40.89%, followed by closed forest (26.53%), together comprising 67% of the total land area. Other natural covers include shrubs (9.78%), grasslands (6.96%), mangroves and bare lands in small patches. Agriculture is also significant, with annual croplands making up 13.44% and perennial croplands about 0.40%, reflecting the municipality’s reliance on corn and rice production. Built-up areas constitute 0.53%, concentrated in urban barangays, while inland waters cover about 0.93%. This composition highlights a landscape where forests and agriculture dominate, but where pressures from cropland expansion and built-up growth intersect with the need for ecosystem protection and sustainable land management.

Figure 3: Land cover (2020) of Penablanca

Source: Research team construct using land cover data from NAMRIA (<https://geoportal.gov.ph/>)

Figure 4: Location of tenurial instruments and protected areas in Penablanca

Source: Research team construct using tenurial instrument and protected areas boundaries from Penablanca LGU

3.1.3 Forest change dynamics

From 2000 to 2024, data from the Tropical Moist Forests (TMF) product (Vancutsem et al., 2021) show that Peñablanca lost about 12,404 hectares of undisturbed forest (see Table 3). During this period, degraded forest areas expanded considerably by more than 9,220 hectares, while deforested land registered only a small increase of 82 hectares. Forest regrowth was notable, with an addition of about 8,046 hectares. Permanent water bodies gained around 29 hectares, whereas other land cover types were reduced by nearly 4,976 hectares. See Fig 5 for the 2024 forest change map and Table 3 for the detailed statistics of change between 2000 and 2024.

Table 3: Penablanca forest change dynamic rates from 2000 to 2024

Forest change dynamics	Area 2000 (ha)	Area 2024 (ha)	Change (2000 - 2024) (ha)	Annual rate (ha/yr)	Annual change rate (%)
Undisturbed forest	84243.78	71840.25	-12403.53	-516.81	-0.61
Degraded forest	5651.55	14873.67	9222.12	384.26	6.80
Deforested land	4623.21	4705.65	82.44	3.43	0.07
Forest regrowth	129.15	8175.33	8046.18	335.26	259.59
Permanent water	592.02	621.27	29.25	1.22	0.21
Other land cover	36320.85	31344.39	-4976.46	-207.35	-0.57

Source: Researchers’ construct using data from <https://forobs.jrc.ec.europa.eu/TMF/data#downloads>

Figure 5: Penablanca forest change dynamic 2024

Source: Research team construct using Tropical Moist Forests (TMF) product datasets (<https://forobs.jrc.ec.europa.eu/TMF/data#downloads>)

3.1.4 Current and future climatic conditions

Penablanca experiences a tropical monsoonal climate classified as Type III under the Coronas system (Coronas, 1920; Corporal-Lodangco, Leslie 2017) similar to the broader Cagayan Valley, including Tuguegarao City (PSA, 2023). The area is generally warm throughout the year, with an annual mean temperature of about 27.2°C. May and June are typically the hottest months, while January is the coolest. The climate has no sharply defined wet or dry season, though conditions are relatively dry from December to April and wetter during the rest of the year. Rainfall is heaviest between July and October, averaging around 1,850 mm annually, with peaks exceeding 330 mm per month in October and November. Average relative humidity is about 78.75%, reflecting persistently moist conditions. Due to its geographic setting along the Sierra Madre Mountains. Penablanca is highly exposed to typhoons, floods, rainfall-induced landslides, and storm surges. These hazards are projected to intensify with climate change, posing growing threats to settlements, agriculture, and ecological resources. See Fig 6 for a climate chart (Zepner et al., 2021) of Tuguegarao City which portrays the same climate condition of Penablanca due to its neighbouring position to the study landscape.

are vulnerable to erosion and flooding. Strict land-use controls are also proposed to prevent settlement encroachment into forest zones, coupled with the promotion of fruit-bearing trees and bamboo plantations that enhance both livelihoods and ecological resilience. To protect long-term soil fertility and forest health, the plan calls for discouraging the use of harmful agrochemicals and promoting organic and sustainable practices. Finally, the municipality emphasizes strengthening community-based forest management (CBFM) systems through local monitoring, surveillance, and co-management approaches, ensuring that conservation measures are both participatory and sustainable.

3.1.6 Current and potential future management challenges

Penablanca municipality faces several potential management challenges in realizing its future land use and forest management visions, primarily the need to balance rapid urbanization, commercial expansion, and eco-tourism development with the protection of its vast forestlands (Municipality of Penablanca, 2020). Settlement encroachment, agricultural pressures, and quarrying may undermine conservation goals, while limited financial, technical, and institutional capacity could constrain large-scale reforestation and agroforestry efforts. Ensuring sustained community participation and compliance is also critical, as livelihood needs may conflict with sustainable practices. Moreover, intensifying climate risks such as flooding, erosion, and typhoons threaten both ecological integrity and development gains. Finally, while eco-tourism offers economic opportunities, unmanaged growth could strain natural resources and habitats, highlighting the need for integrated, adaptive management approaches.

3.2 Balasig Watershed

3.2.1 Socio-demographic

The Balasig Watershed is a makeup of technically, 3 municipalities in Isabela Province of Cagayan Valley, constituting 10 barangays from Cabagan, 20 barangays from Tumauni and 1 barangay from San Pablo municipalities making up a total land area of 263.98km² (26396 hectares). Considering the above highlighted barangays in the Watershed, the area’s population as at 2024 stood at 53915 with a steady increasing growth rate since 2015 (see Table 4 and Fig 7) and population density around 2.04 person per hectare. The Watershed is considered to be an intermediate rural-urban area with agriculture, mainly corn and rice farming as the major source of livelihood for local inhabitants.

Table 4: Total population of Balasig Watershed from 2010 to 2024

Year	Total population
2010	42,809
2015	47,857
2020	51,054
2024	53,915

Source: <https://psa.gov.ph/>

Figure 7: Population growth rate trend (annual % change) of Balasig Watershed from 2010 to 2024

Source: <https://psa.gov.ph/>

3.2.2 Land use and topography

The Balasig watershed is characterized by a diverse topography, ranging from flat plains along the Cagayan River to steep and mountainous terrains forming part of the Sierra Madre range in the east (Fig. 8). The lower-lying western areas are generally used for intensive agriculture and settlements, while the rolling to steeply sloping lands transition into forest, grassland, and shrub-dominated landscapes. The most rugged zones are primarily suited for forest cover and watershed protection, limiting agricultural use but serving crucial ecological functions such as water regulation and erosion control.

The Balasig Watershed spans a diverse landscape of 26,368 hectares, with land use dominated by agriculture, particularly annual croplands that cover 52.12% of the total area according to National Mapping and Resource

Information Authority (NAMRIA) land cover 2020 (see Table 5 and Fig. 9). Forests remain significant, with open forest accounting making up 20.01% and closed forest (3.19%), together representing just over 23% of the watershed. Shrubs cover 13.12%, reflecting transitional or regenerating vegetation, while grasslands occupy 8.83% across the watershed. Other land cover classes make up smaller shares: built-up areas 1.61%, water bodies 0.75%, and bare lands just 0.38%. This composition highlights a watershed where agriculture is the dominant land use, supported by substantial forest and shrub cover that play vital roles in regulating water flow, protecting soils, and maintaining ecological balance, alongside small but important areas of settlements and water bodies.

Figure 8: Topography of Balasig Watershed

Source: Research team construct using municipality and barangay administrative boundaries from Cabagan and Tumauini LGU and Balasig Watershed boundary from Region II DENR-CDD and elevation map using DEM from Aster (<https://asterweb.jpl.nasa.gov/gdem.asp>).

Table 5: Balasig Watershed land cover coverage (ha and km²) and percentage of coverage to total land area

Land cover class	Area (ha)	Area (km ²)	% Coverage
Closed forest	841.95	8.42	3.19
Open forest	5274.81	52.75	20.01
Shrubs	3458.43	34.58	13.12
Bareland	98.91	0.99	0.38
Grassland	2328.84	23.29	8.83
Annual cropland	13741.38	137.41	52.12
Built_up	424.44	4.24	1.61
Water	198.18	1.98	0.75

Source: Researchers' construct using land cover data from NAMRIA <https://geoportal.gov.ph/>

Figure 9: Land cover (2020) of Balasig Watershed

Source: Research team construct using land cover data from NAMRIA (<https://geoportal.gov.ph/>).

Figure 10: Location of tenurial instruments and protected areas in Balasig Watershed

Source: Research team construct using Tenurial instrument and protected areas boundaries from Cabagan and Tumauni LGU.

3.2.3 Forest change dynamics

Based on the Tropical Moist Forests (TMF) product (Vancutsem et al., 2021) datasets from 2000 to 2024, Balasig Watershed recorded a reduction of about 2,021 hectares in undisturbed forest (see Table 6). Over the same period, degraded forests expanded by approximately 1,418 hectares, while deforested land decreased by about 124 hectares. Forest regrowth reached around 1,350 hectares, permanent water increased slightly by 3.5 hectares, and other land cover declined by about 626 hectares. See Fig 11 for the 2024 forest change map and Table 6 for the statistics of change between 2000 and 2024.

Table 6: Balasig Watershed forest change dynamic rates from 2000 to 2024

Forest change dynamics	Area 2000 (ha)	Area 2024 (ha)	Change (2000 - 2024) (ha)	Annual rate (ha/yr)	Annual change rate (%)
Undisturbed forest	6803.1	4782.24	-2020.86	-84.20	-1.24
Degraded forest	597.06	2014.83	1417.77	59.07	9.89
Deforested land	926.19	802.62	-123.57	-5.15	-0.56
Forest regrowth	3.24	1352.79	1349.55	56.23	1735.53
Permanent water	132.48	135.99	3.51	0.15	0.11
Other land cover	19331.01	18704.61	-626.40	-26.10	-0.14

Source: Researchers’ construct using data from <https://forobs.jrc.ec.europa.eu/TMF/data#downloads>

Figure 11: Balasig Watershed Forest change dynamic 2024

Source: Research team construct using Tropical Moist Forests (TMF) product datasets (<https://forobs.jrc.ec.europa.eu/TMF/data#downloads>)

3.2.4 Current and future climatic conditions

Balasig Watershed’s climate is characterized by high average temperatures of about 27.3°C, high rainfall variability, and an increasing frequency of extreme weather events. Annual precipitation is considerable, averaging 2,023 mm, with the driest months occurring early in the year and the wet season extending from July through December. October is typically the wettest month, with rainfall peaking significantly during this period. Most parts of the watershed lie within the flood-prone Cagayan River Basin, making them especially vulnerable to typhoons, prolonged rains, and occasional droughts. Historical observations point to rising average temperatures and shifting rainfall patterns, further heightening risks of flooding, crop failure, and associated health concerns. See Fig. 12 for Cabagan climate chart (Zepner et al., 2021) which depicts the situation of the entire Balasig Watershed.

Projected future climate scenarios suggest that Cabagan will experience intensified climate hazards, especially during the Northeast Monsoon (Amihan) and Southwest Monsoon (Habagat) seasons. Expected trends include rising temperatures, more severe floods, and extended dry spells, all of which pose threats to agriculture, water resources, and local infrastructure. The most affected sectors are expected to be agriculture, fisheries, water supply, and public health.

Figure 12: Climate chart showing mean precipitation and temperature in Cabagan from 1993 to 2022

Source: <https://climatecharts.net/>

3.2.5 Future land use and forest-related management visions

According to comprehensive land use plans (CLUP) of Cabagan and Tumauni, the future land use and forest-related management vision for the Balasig Watershed (consideration of Cabagan and Tumauni municipalities visions) is centered on achieving a balanced model of sustainable development where urban expansion, agricultural productivity, and forest conservation coexist to strengthen both ecological resilience and socio-economic growth (Municipality of Cabagan, 2018; Municipality of Tumauni, 2023). In line with the broader aspirations of Cabagan and Tumauni, the watershed is envisioned to host modest but strategically planned urban growth, with infrastructure improvements such as enhanced road networks, flood control systems, water supply facilities, and community service centers designed to support increasing population and economic activities. Importantly, this urban and economic development is deliberately planned to avoid significant encroachment into agricultural and forest zones, recognizing the long-term value of these lands for food security, biodiversity, and disaster resilience.

The vision acknowledges that the Balasig watershed is particularly vulnerable to climate-induced hazards, including flooding, droughts, and landslides, given its varied topography and reliance on the Cagayan River and tributaries. Future proposals therefore emphasize strengthening disaster risk management through integrated land use planning that incorporates floodplain zoning, slope stabilization, and investment in drainage systems

and early warning infrastructure. Ecosystem-based solutions such as watershed rehabilitation, mangrove reforestation along riverbanks, and the maintenance of riparian vegetation are prioritized to enhance natural flood regulation and water retention capacity. These measures are aimed not only at reducing climate risks but also at securing livelihoods that depend on the watershed's agricultural and water resources.

On the forestry side, the Balasig watershed's management vision highlights strict monitoring and protection of the Sierra Madre Forest ecosystems, including portions overlapping with the Northern Sierra Madre Natural Park (NSMNP). Both Cabagan and Tumauni emphasize the critical role of forests in climate regulation, soil conservation, water cycle maintenance, and biodiversity protection. Future initiatives shall therefore focus on reinforcing anti-illegal logging campaigns, expanding reforestation and agroforestry in degraded upland and high-sloped areas, and promoting biodiversity corridors to sustain ecological connectivity. Moreover, the vision incorporates sustainable forest-based livelihoods such as eco-tourism, non-timber forest products, and community-managed forest enterprises as strategies to reduce pressure on natural resources while creating alternative income sources.

Governance and social participation are at the heart of these future proposals. The watershed's management shall be strengthened through multi-stakeholder partnerships involving local governments, national agencies, civil society organizations, and local communities. Capacity-building programs shall empower residents with the knowledge and tools to actively engage in forest protection, sustainable farming, and responsible land use practices. Education and environmental awareness initiatives are also envisioned to foster a culture of stewardship across generations.

Hence, the future vision for the Balasig watershed combines sustainable urban growth, climate-adaptive infrastructure, resilient agriculture, and strong forest protection measures. By integrating ecological sustainability into economic and social development, the watershed is envisioned to evolve into a climate-resilient and ecologically balanced landscape, ensuring that its natural resources continue to provide essential ecosystem services while supporting the aspirations of its people for prosperity and security.

3.2.6 Current and potential future management challenges

The management challenges facing the Balasig watershed reflect a combination of institutional, technical, financial, and socio-political constraints as described in the CLUPs (Municipality of Cabagan, 2018; Municipality of Tumauni, 2023). A critical concern is the establishment of an effective results-based monitoring and evaluation (RBME) system to track the wide range of interventions and ensure that resources are allocated and utilized efficiently. Weak linkages between planning, budgeting, and execution often result in delays, inefficiencies, and potential misallocation of resources. At the same time, Tumauni's CLUP highlights the financial risks of securing sufficient funding for large-scale infrastructure and environmental programs, compounded by technical complexities and logistical hurdles in implementing watershed management projects across challenging terrain. Regulatory and compliance demands further strain local capacity, while safety, quality management, and operational issues create risks during project execution. Market uncertainties and shifting land use dynamics also affect long-term project viability, requiring adaptive strategies. Finally, political and social risks remain significant, as the effectiveness of management efforts depends on community acceptance, stakeholder participation, and sustained local support. Together, these interlinked challenges underscore the need for integrated governance, evidence-based decision-making, and strong institutional coordination to ensure that Balasig watershed interventions achieve their intended ecological and socio-economic outcomes.

3.3 Maasin

3.3.1 Socio-demographic

Maasin is a City and the capital of Southern Leyte Province in Eastern Visayas region, consisting of 70 barangays. The city mainly functions as the administrative, commercial, and religious center of the province. The city covers a total land area of 20,949 hectares (209.49 km²), predominantly covered with agricultural land including coconut-based farms, rice fields, and upland production areas. As of the 2024, Maasin had a population of 85,486, which is a decrease from their 2020 population as presented in Table 7 and a decreasing growth rate trend since 2010 and presented in Fig. 13. The gross population density of Maasin is about 408 persons per km² (4.08 persons per hectare), with the majority concentrated in the coastal barangays. Agriculture remains the primary source of livelihood, dominated by mainly, coconut, and others including rice, abaca, and root crop production, while fisheries and aquaculture also play a vital role in coastal communities. Complementing this base are small-scale trade and commerce in the Poblacion (city’s core) barangays, public services as the provincial capital, cottage industries such as food processing and handicrafts, and an emerging eco-tourism and pilgrimage sector driven by the city’s natural attractions and religious sites (City of Maasin, 2016).

Table 7: Total population of Maasin from 2010 to 2024

Year	Total Population
2010	81,250
2015	85,560
2020	87,446
2024	85,486

Source: <https://psa.gov.ph/>

Figure 13: Population growth rate trend (annual % change) of Maasin from 2010 to 2024

Source: <https://psa.gov.ph/>

3.3.2 Land use and topography

Maasin’s topography is generally uneven, with a mix of narrow coastal plains, inland valleys, and extensive hilly to mountainous terrain dominating much of its land area. Elevations range from sea level along the Bohol Sea coast to over 716 meters above sea level in the upland barangays (Fig. 14), with slopes exceeding 18% across more than half of the total area. The steep slopes and upland ridges serve as important watersheds and forestlands, while low-lying plains and river valleys provide limited space for settlements, irrigated rice fields, and coconut-based agriculture. This varied terrain strongly influences land use, with urban growth concentrated along the flatter coastal zones, while the uplands remain largely devoted to forestry, agroforestry, and biodiversity conservation that are vital to the city’s ecological stability and climate resilience.

Maasin City’s land use composition is predominantly agriculture, with perennial croplands mainly coconut plantations, abaca, and other tree crops occupying about 61.27% of the total land area according to National Mapping and Resource Information Authority (NAMRIA) landcover 2020 (see Table 8 and Fig. 15). Shrubland (considered as forest land areas according to Maasin City LGU) is the next largest land cover type, covering about 26.23%, mostly in upland areas. Built-up areas, which include residential, commercial, and institutional spaces, account for about (4.2%), concentrated along the coastal Poblacion barangays and selected growth centers. Annual croplands, largely rice and other seasonal crops, occupy 3.95%, while grasslands cover 2.28%, often used for grazing or left idle. The city also maintains important coastal ecosystems, with 242 hectares (1.16%) of mangroves providing fishery resources and shoreline protection. This composition highlights the dominance of perennial crop-based agriculture, the growing extent of shrublands, and the relatively small but expanding footprint of built-up areas that reflect Maasin’s gradual urbanization (mainly infrastructure expansion) alongside its strong dependence on agriculture and natural ecosystems.

Figure 14: Topography of Maasin

Source: Research team construct using municipality and barangay administrative boundaries from Maasin LGU and elevation map using DEM from Aster (<https://asterweb.jpl.nasa.gov/gdem.asp>)

Table 8: Maasin land cover coverage (ha and km²) and percentage of coverage to total land area

Land cover class	Area (ha)	Area (km ²)	% Coverage
Open forest	146.79	1.47	0.7
Mangrove	242.73	2.43	1.16
Shrubs	5496.12	54.96	26.23
Bareland	0.9	0.01	0
Grassland	476.55	4.77	2.28
Annual cropland	827.37	8.27	3.95
Perennial cropland	12837.33	128.37	61.27
Built_up	878.76	8.79	4.2
Water	42.84	0.43	0.21

Source: Researchers' construct using landcover data from NAMRIA <https://geoportal.gov.ph/>

Figure 15: Land cover (2020) of Maasin

Source: Research team construct using land cover data from NAMRIA (<https://geoportal.gov.ph/>)

Figure 16: Location of tenurial instrument areas in Maasin

Source: Research team construct using Tenurial instrument areas boundaries from Maasin City LGU

3.3.3 Forest change dynamics

According to the Tropical Moist Forests (TMF) product (Vancutsem et al., 2021) datasets from 2000 to 2024, Maasin’s undisturbed forest declined by about 70%, with a loss of over 10,000 hectares (see Table 9). During the same period, degraded forests increased by more than 7,200 hectares, while deforested land expanded by about 2,800 hectares. Forest regrowth covered only 277 hectares, permanent water increased slightly by 2.6 hectares, and other land cover decreased by about 179 hectares. See Fig 17 for the 2024 forest status and Table 9 for the statistics of change between 2000 and 2024.

Table 9: Maasin forest change dynamic rates from 2000 to 2024

Forest change dynamics	Area 2000 (ha)	Area 2024 (ha)	Change (2000 - 2024) (ha)	Annual rate (ha/yr)	Annual change rate (%)
Undisturbed forest	14418.72	4281.84	-10136.88	-422.37	-2.93
Degraded forest	1207.89	8412.03	7204.14	300.17	24.85
Deforested land	2448.36	5279.58	2831.22	117.97	4.82
Forest regrowth	17.01	294.48	277.47	11.56	67.97
Permanent water	42.48	45.09	2.61	0.11	0.26
Other land cover	3291.21	3112.65	-178.56	-7.44	-0.23

Source: Researchers’ construct using data from <https://forobs.jrc.ec.europa.eu/TMF/data#downloads>

Figure 17: Maasin Forest change dynamic 2024

Source: Research team construct using Tropical Moist Forests (TMF) product datasets (<https://forobs.jrc.ec.europa.eu/TMF/data#downloads>)

3.3.4 Current and future climatic conditions

Maasin experiences a tropical rainforest climate characterized by consistently warm temperatures and high rainfall year-round. The mean annual temperature is about 27.2°C, with monthly averages ranging from 26.2°C to 28.4°C, while total annual precipitation reaches 2,704.5 mm, reflecting a persistently humid environment. Rainfall is lowest between April and May (127.7–145.2 mm) and peaks in December and January (326.4–356.9 mm). In recent years, the city has increasingly experienced the impacts of climate change in the form of erratic weather patterns, intensified typhoons, prolonged droughts, and rising sea levels. These changes have disrupted agriculture, water resources, and local livelihoods, while also amplifying the city’s exposure to climate-related hazards such as landslides, flooding, storm surges, and coastal erosion, particularly in vulnerable barangays located along coastlines and steep uplands. See climate chart (Zepner et al., 2021) in Fig 18 depicting the climate situation in Maasin.

Climate projections for the city suggest a continued rise in average temperature and an increase in the frequency and severity of extreme weather events. Sea level rise is expected to affect coastal barangays, potentially displacing communities and impacting infrastructure and ecosystems such as mangroves and fisheries. Increased rainfall variability is also anticipated, with a higher risk of both droughts and flash floods, disrupting food security and water supply.

residential and commercial uses, the total agricultural production area is projected to increase by over 8.80 km² through the conversion of grasslands and idle areas into productive spaces for livestock, poultry, and diversified crops. This reflects a dual strategy of protecting prime agricultural zones from conversion while reorienting less productive lands into sustainable agri-livelihood hubs. Industrial development shall also be carefully integrated, with new agro-processing facilities and light to medium-scale industries designated for barangays such as Tam-is, Panan-awan, and Libhu. These zones shall be regulated with strict pollution control measures and buffer requirements to safeguard nearby residential communities, reflecting the city's emphasis on climate-smart and environmentally sound industrial growth.

Tourism, both eco-based and religious, forms another cornerstone of Maasin's future land use vision. Natural attractions such as Hapitan Beach, the Mahayahay Mangrove Site, Guinsohotan Cave, and Cagnituan Lagoon shall be developed as eco-tourism destinations, supported by improved access, sanitation, and conservation programs that ensure long-term ecological sustainability. At the same time, the city's renowned pilgrimage sites including Monte Cueva, Jalleca Hills, and the Maasin Cathedral shall benefit from infrastructure investments in access roads, safety, and visitor facilities to attract both local and international pilgrims. To reinforce cultural identity and diversify tourism offerings, the city shall also preserve and promote its rich heritage, including Spanish-era ancestral houses, garrisons, and the Maasin Museum, with support for signage, guided tours, and partnerships with local stakeholders and the Diocese of Maasin. These initiatives are expected to strengthen tourism as a key economic driver while ensuring cultural continuity and community participation.

Central to the city's long-term sustainability is its forest-related management strategy. Maasin recognizes the ecological importance of its protected and production forests, which shall remain intact through 2025 and beyond as a critical foundation for biodiversity conservation, climate regulation, and slope stabilization in landslide-prone upland barangays. Strict prohibitions on tree-cutting shall continue in protected forest zones, watersheds, and mangrove areas to safeguard water supply, soil integrity, and coastal protection. At the same time, production forest areas shall be managed through sustainable approaches, including reforestation, agroforestry, and private tree plantation development, ensuring a continuous supply of timber and non-timber resources while maintaining ecological corridors. Multi-story agroforestry systems shall be promoted in rehabilitation zones, particularly along riverbanks, where buffer zones ranging from 3 to 40 meters shall be enforced depending on the surrounding land use, to mitigate flooding, prevent soil erosion, and support biodiversity recovery. Coastal and mangrove reforestation shall also be expanded as part of the city's ridge-to-reef strategy, enhancing natural defenses against storm surges and sea-level rise.

To ensure that these future land use and forest management strategies are effectively implemented, Maasin's CLUP includes strict zoning ordinances supported by a Monitoring, Review, and Evaluation Team composed of zoning officers, deputized barangay monitors, and other enforcement bodies (City of Maasin, 2016). These mechanisms shall guarantee compliance with environmental laws, development permits, and spatial policies. Furthermore, annual budget allocations and continuous information, education, and communication (IEC) campaigns shall strengthen public participation, transparency, and awareness. The CLUP also identifies overlay zones for biodiversity conservation and eco-tourism to prioritize the protection of sensitive habitats and landscapes amidst competing development pressures. Taken together, these future land use and forest management proposals chart a development pathway for Maasin City that harmonizes urban growth with ecological resilience, making it a model for sustainable land governance in Southern Leyte.

3.3.6 Current and potential future management challenges

The CLUP of Maasin City outlines several management challenges that could affect the successful implementation of its land use vision (City of Maasin, 2016). One major challenge is the presence of land use conflicts, especially in areas where urban expansion encroaches upon agricultural and forest lands, potentially leading to the loss of ecologically sensitive areas. The city also faces the difficulty of enforcing zoning regulations and environmental policies due to limited technical personnel, and inadequate monitoring capacity at the barangay level. Additionally, vulnerability to natural hazards such as landslides in upland barangays, and flooding,

storm surges, and tsunamis in coastal areas poses a significant threat to infrastructure and land use planning. Climate change further exacerbates these risks, challenging the resilience of both natural systems and local livelihoods. Lastly, the coordination among various stakeholders and the need for continuous information dissemination, capacity building, and proper budgeting for CLUP implementation present ongoing administrative and governance hurdles.

3.4 Silago

3.4.1 Socio-demographic

Silago municipality is considered a rural area located in the province of Southern Leyte, fronting the Pacific Ocean, and is composed of 15 barangays (Cadiz et al., 2022). It has a total land area of approximately 180.45 km² (19,039 hectares), characterized by a mix of coastal plains and extensive upland terrain dominated by forestlands. The municipality’s population was recorded to be around 14,677 in 2024, with an increasing population growth rate since 2015 (see Fig. 19), and a population density of about 81.32 person per km² (0.81 person per ha). Silago remains largely rural, with livelihoods centred on agriculture and fisheries, mainly coconut and other crops including rice, root crops, vegetables, and abaca. Fishing and aquaculture in its coastal barangays provide secondary income sources, while livestock raising is practiced mainly at the household level. Despite its abundant natural resources, the municipality faces socio-economic challenges, including poverty, limited infrastructure, and high vulnerability to typhoons, floods, and landslides, which constrain its economic diversification. Nonetheless, its intact forests, fertile valleys, and rich marine areas present opportunities for eco-tourism, agroforestry, and sustainable resource management to support long-term development (Cadiz et al., 2022).

Table 10: Total population of Silago from 2010 to 2024

Year	Total Population
2010	12,310
2015	12,775
2020	13,116
2024	14,677

Source: <https://psa.gov.ph/>

Figure 19: Population growth rate trend (annual % change) of Silago from 2010 to 2024

Source: <https://psa.gov.ph/>

3.4.2 Land use and topography

Silago’s topography is characterized by a mix of coastal plains, rolling lowlands, and extensive hilly to mountainous terrain that dominates much of its interior landscape. Elevations rise sharply from near sea level

along the Pacific coast to rugged uplands up to 967 meters above sea level (Fig. 20), with slopes of over 30–50% covering large portions of the municipality.

Figure 20: Topography of Silago

Source: Research team construct using municipality and barangay administrative boundaries from Silago LGU and elevation map using DEM from Aster (<https://asterweb.jpl.nasa.gov/gdem.asp>)

These steep and varied landscapes constrain large-scale settlement and mechanized farming but support rich forest cover, watersheds, and river systems that provide vital ecological services such as water regulation, soil stability, and biodiversity conservation, while the more level coastal and valley areas are primarily used for rice paddies, coconut plantations, and small-scale agriculture. Silago’s land use composition is dominated by forests and agricultural lands, reflecting its rural and resource-based economy. Forestlands occupy nearly half of the municipality’s 19,039-hectare area, with open forest covering (39.62%) and closed forest (6.64%), while

mangroves account for only (0.01%) along the coast according to National Mapping and Resource Information Authority (NAMRIA) landcover 2020 (see Table 11 and Fig. 21). Shrublands cover (19.58%) and grasslands (7.66%), much of which are former forest areas transitioning into degraded lands. Agriculture is extensive, with perennial croplands (primarily coconut) occupying (20.33%) and annual croplands (including rice and root crops) covering (4.56%). Built-up areas remain relatively small making up (1.17%), concentrated in the poblacion and coastal barangays, while water bodies cover 75.96 hectares (0.42%). This land use pattern highlights the ecological importance of Silago’s forests and watersheds, the dominance of coconut-based agriculture, and the pressures of land degradation and limited urban expansion. It also underscores the need for sustainable land management and nature-based solutions to balance conservation, food security, and climate resilience.

Figure 21: Land cover (2020) of Silago

Source: Research team construct using land cover data from NAMRIA (<https://geoportal.gov.ph/>)

Table 11: Silago 2020 land cover coverage (ha and km²) and percentage of coverage to total land area

Land cover class	Area (ha)	Area (km ²)	% Coverage
Closed forest	1197.81	11.98	6.64
Open forest	7152.3	71.52	39.62
Mangrove	1.89	0.02	0.01
Shrubs	3533.94	35.34	19.58
Bareland	2.16	0.02	0.01
Grassland	1381.59	13.82	7.66
Annual cropland	823.86	8.24	4.56
Perennial cropland	3671.1	36.71	20.33
Built_up	211.77	2.12	1.17
Water	75.96	0.76	0.42

Source: Researchers' construct using land cover data from NAMRIA <https://geoportal.gov.ph/>

3.4.3 Forest change dynamics

According to the Tropical Moist Forests (TMF) product (Vancutsem et al., 2021) datasets from 2000 to 2024, Silago's undisturbed forest was reduced by about 2,200 hectares (see Table 12). During the same period, degraded forests increased by more than 1,570 hectares, while deforested land expanded by about 137 hectares. Forest regrowth covered 1,231 hectares, permanent water increased slightly by 0.6 hectares, and other land cover decreased by about 739 hectares. See Fig 23 for the 2024 forest change map and Table 12 for the statistics of change between 2000 and 2024.

Table 12: Silago forest change dynamic rates from 2000 to 2024

Forest change dynamics	Area 2000 (ha)	Area 2024 (ha)	Change (2000 - 2024) (ha)	Annual rate (ha/yr)	Annual change rate (%)
Undisturbed forest	14244.93	12045.24	-2199.69	-91.65	-0.64
Degraded forest	551.61	2122.74	1571.13	65.46	11.87
Deforested land	1772.82	1909.44	136.62	5.69	0.32
Forest regrowth	20.07	1250.64	1230.57	51.27	255.47
Permanent water	7.38	8.01	0.63	0.03	0.36
Other land cover	1877.04	1137.78	-739.26	-30.80	-1.64

Source: Researchers' construct using data from <https://forobs.jrc.ec.europa.eu/TMF/data#downloads>

3.4.4 Current and future climatic conditions

Silago is highly exposed to climate-related hazards such as typhoons, heavy rainfall, floods, storm surges, landslides, and tsunamis. Its prevailing climate is Type II under the Modified Corona Classification (Coronas, 1920; Corporal-Lodangco, Leslie 2017), characterized by the absence of a dry season and a pronounced rainy period from November to February. The average annual temperature is 26.9°C, with minimal variation across the year (25.8°C–27.9°C monthly), while precipitation is exceptionally high (3,724.2 mm) annually. December and January are the wettest months, receiving 583.9 mm and 486.3 mm of rainfall, respectively, while July and September are relatively drier, though still wet by global standards, with 192.7 mm and 197.6 mm. Historical data indicate increasingly erratic climate patterns, with more extreme hot and rainy seasons already affecting local livelihoods,

reinforcing Silago’s classification as a consistently warm and very wet tropical rainforest zone. See climate chart (Zepner et al., 2021) in Fig. 24 depicting the climate situation for Silago.

Based on climate projections, Silago is expected to experience significant warming, with temperature increases of up to 2.2°C by the 2050s, especially during the warm-dry months of April and May. Rainfall is projected to decline during the dry season and increase during the wet season, exacerbating the risk of droughts, flooding, and other extreme events. Inland areas, where most forests are located, are particularly vulnerable to these changes, while coastal zones face threats from sea-level rise and more intense storm surges.

Figure 22: Location of tenorial instrument areas in Silago

Source: Research team construct using Tenorial instrument areas boundaries from Silago LGU

Figure 23: Maasin Forest change dynamic 2024

Source: Research team construct using Tropical Moist Forests (TMF) product datasets (<https://forobs.jrc.ec.europa.eu/TMF/data#downloads>)

3.4.5 Future land use and forest-related management visions

Silago’s future land use and forest management vision, as articulated in its 2022 - 2032 Comprehensive Land Use Plan (CLUP), is based on sustainability, climate resilience, and inclusive development. Central to this vision is the strengthening of Community-Based Forest Management (CBFM) programs, which are recognized as a cornerstone for forest conservation while simultaneously enhancing the livelihoods of forest-dependent communities (Cadiz et al., 2022). The municipality seeks to build the capacity of these communities to sustainably manage forest resources, reduce pressures from agricultural expansion, and adopt alternative livelihoods such as agroforestry, eco-tourism, and other climate-resilient enterprises. By integrating local knowledge with scientific forest management practices, Silago aims to ensure both ecological integrity and socio-economic benefits for its population.

Given the projected impacts of climate change including rising temperatures, prolonged dry spells, and intensified extreme weather, Silago's forest management strategies shall incorporate adaptive measures. These include reforestation using native and drought-resistant species, the establishment of firebreaks and buffer zones to mitigate wildfire risks, and improved forest fire surveillance and control systems. Sustainable harvesting practices shall be promoted to balance economic needs with ecological protection. In addition, the municipality plans to invest in modern monitoring systems, utilizing remote sensing and GIS technologies to track land cover changes, detect illegal logging, and monitor forest health in real-time.

Finally, the CLUP underscores the importance of environmental education, participatory governance, and stakeholder engagement in shaping the future of Silago's forests. By fostering a shared sense of stewardship, the municipality envisions building a resilient landscape where forests, watersheds, and agricultural areas are managed in harmony, ensuring that ecological sustainability underpins social and economic progress.

3.4.6 Current and potential future management challenges

The CLUP identifies several management challenges in Silago, particularly in relation to forest conservation and land use (Cadiz et al., 2022). One major challenge is the ongoing pressure from agricultural expansion into forestlands, driven by the demand for more farming space and the widespread establishment of coconut plantations, which often become the final land use after forest clearing. This is compounded by weak enforcement of land use regulations, limited monitoring capacity, and insufficient coordination among government agencies and local stakeholders. Additionally, road construction and infrastructure development increase accessibility to remote forest areas, accelerating land conversion and forest fragmentation. Illegal logging, though less widespread, remains a concern due to regional timber scarcity and limited livelihood options for upland communities. These pressures are further intensified by climate change impacts, such as increased temperatures and prolonged dry periods, which can reduce forest productivity and increase fire risks. Addressing these challenges requires stronger institutional support, integrated land use planning, community involvement, and enhanced climate adaptation strategies.

4 Conclusion

In summary, the four study landscapes thus, Penablanca, Balasig Watershed, Maasin, and Silago share common pressures from agriculture and climate-related hazards but exhibit distinct land use and climatic characteristics. Penablanca, an intermediate rural - urban landscape, is heavily forested, and livelihood sources mainly powered by agriculture, quarrying, and eco-tourism. Its climate, with no distinct wet or dry season but heavy rainfall from July to October. Balasig Watershed is also considered an intermediate rural-urban area which is dominated by agriculture, with over half of its land planted with corn and rice, which is also the major livelihood source for localities. The watershed increasingly experiences situations of drought irrespective of the continuous wet periods and the conditions of high rainfall variability and shifting weather patterns. Maasin, the most urbanized landscape and provincial capital with 85,486 residents, has over 65% of its land area under perennial croplands such as coconut, which is also a major livelihood source and places stress on its remaining forests. Its climate is marked by irregular rainfall pattern, and exposure to coastal hazards such as storm surges and erosion. Silago, by contrast, is the smallest and considered a rural and the least populated landscape amongst the four study landscapes. Silago is also dominated with forest cover and has traces of perennial cropland (coconut) expansion, which is also a major livelihood source. Silago is also part of type II climate zone, with no dry season and a pronounced rainy period from November to February, making it highly exposed to typhoons, floods, and even tsunamis.

Across all four landscapes, agriculture remains the main livelihood source and driver of land use change, and they all also face similar hazards including droughts, typhoons, floods, and even tsunamis. However, the differences across the four landscapes provide an important basis for analysing varied dynamics pertaining to degradation drivers and ecosystem service provision and their implication for future land use changes as well as different NBS

implementation patterns to ensure a balanced conservation and improved livelihood conditions in different locations of the Philippines and other tropical regions

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